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Report real-life exposure profiles from re-analysis of existing HBM mixture data

Deliverable Report D15.3

WP15 - Mixtures, HBM and human health risks

Task 15.1 Statistical methods to identify mixtures in HBM data

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2 Glossary

HBM	Human Biomonitoring
SNMU	Sparse Non-negative Under-approximation Method
LOD	Limit of Detection
LOQ	Limit of Quantification
PCA	Principal Component Analysis
WP	Work Package

Disclaimer

This deliverable is based on simulated data. All conclusions drawn and interpretations made are for illustration purposes only and therefore should not be interpreted in terms of their biological relevance.

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3 Abstract/Summary

One of the aims of HBM4EU is to “improve the precision and efficacy of HBM to inform science, policy and regulatory actions with respect to dealing with mixtures”. This is the domain of WP15. In this context an important aspect of dealing with mixtures involves providing a description of their occurrence in HBM data. This deliverable describes several statistical approaches that provide such insights and in addition provides statistical methods that can be used to gain insight into the determinants of mixture profiles in HBM data. The deliverable provides practical instructions on how to apply the statistical methods using the R language. At each step we provide a demonstration application using a dataset that was simulated to represent a real-life example of HBM data. We also provide a brief description of the potential inferences that can be made when applying the methods on real-life data.

However, it is important to stress that all conclusions drawn and interpretations made are for illustration purposes only and therefore should not be interpreted in terms of their biological relevance. All methods discussed in this deliverable are ready for application in HBM datasets available within HBM4EU.

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4 Introduction

Humans are exposed to a myriad of concurrent and protracted environmental, occupational, dietary, lifestyle and consumer product exposures. These mixtures of exposure can form an almost infinite number of different combinations of chemicals, which makes the exposure and risk assessment extremely challenging. In the context of this document a mixture is defined as the common occurrence of chemical substances or their metabolites in the human body at a given time point. The overall aim of “WP15 Mixtures, HBM and human health risks” is to improve the precision and efficacy of HBM to inform science, policy and regulatory actions with respect to dealing with mixtures. The work in WP15 is broken down in three tasks among which task 15.1 “Re-analysis of existing data on mixtures from earlier HBM studies using a key set of summary indicators”, consisting of statistical analyses on existing data with focus on exposure profiles that take into account coincidental exposures.

Within the HBM4EU consortium datasets containing Human Biomonitoring data will become available. Within HBM4EU input data will be prepared using the HBM4EU Data Template, and variables will be coded following the HBM4EU Codebook. Task 15.1 pertains to the development of statistical approaches that describe potential mixture patterns in this data. In this deliverable we present a number of complementary approaches that can be applied to HBM4EU datasets to achieve this goal. Due to delays in biomonitoring datasets becoming available within HBM4EU this deliverable is based on a simulated dataset, which emulates the typical structure of a biomonitoring dataset. A more in detail description of this simulation dataset is given in section 5. This is a guidance document for the analysis of HBM mixture data, accompanied by plots and corresponding R-code. For all analyses a brief description of the merits and limitations of the approach will be given. This document includes necessary Rcode to run all analysis steps, a separate Rscript with all code will also be made available.

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5 Dataset

5.1 R language

For this document it is assumed that the required software R (<https://www.r-project.org/>) and RStudio (<http://rstudio.org>) is installed and that the user has some basic knowledge about the R language. To straighten out which is: R is the name of the programming language itself and RStudio is a convenient interface.

5.1.1 Required packages

For the purpose of HBM mixture analysis different packages are used besides the base functions of R.

```
assertthat plyr abind lme4 glmnet circlize ggraph mice igraph ggm gplots ggplot2 RColorBrewer
FactoMineR tidyverse glmnet stabs huge igraph plotly
```

5.1.2 Working directory

To ensure to start with a clean session, the current working environment will be cleared and the correct working directory is set.

```
rm(list = ls())
PathName = dirname(getActiveDocumentContext())$path
setwd(PathName)
getwd()
```

The simulated datafile needs to be loaded. This code shows how to load your own file(s), the datafile has to be one the following file-types: `.Rdata` or `.rda` or `.xls` or `.xlsx`.

```
InputPath = paste(PathName, "/Input/", sep = "")
#OutputPath = paste(PathName, "/Output/", sep = "")
FileName = list.files(path = InputPath)
# load(paste(InputPath, FileName, sep = ""))
FilePath = paste(InputPath, FileName, sep = "")

import_hbm_data <- function (PathToFile) {

  assertthat::assert_that(file.exists(PathToFile))

  if (assertthat::has_extension(PathToFile, "rda") |
      assertthat::has_extension(PathToFile, "RData")
  ) {
    load(PathToFile, envir = .GlobalEnv)
  } else if (assertthat::has_extension(PathToFile, "xls") |
             assertthat::has_extension(PathToFile, "xlsx")
  ) {
    sheets <- readxl::excel_sheets(PathToFile)
    data <- mapply(function (sheet) readxl::read_excel(PathToFile, sheet = sheet),
                  sheets)

    # data <- data[-which(names(data) == "STUDYINFO")]
    assign("alldata", data, envir = .GlobalEnv)
  } else {
    stop(paste(PathToFile, "is not of the correct type,
               file-type has to be one of: .rda, .RData, .xls or .xlsx"))
  }
}

import_hbm_data(FilePath)
```

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5.2 Simulated dataset

For the purpose of this document the simulated dataset is called `HBM4EUData`. This dataset consists of 1200 observations and 87 different exposure variables. The variables cover 8 `PFAS`, 8 `PCBs`, 26 `flame retardants`, 26 `heavy metals`, 9 `phenols` and 10 `phthalates`. These exposure variables are typically measured in blood or urine. At different points in this script the group of `PCBs` and `flame retardants` will be taken as an example. The dataset also includes explanatory variables, or determinants. The 4 explanatory variables in this dataset are called `PM25_T`, `Ben_preg`, `SUGAR` and `ALCO`. Examples of real determinants could be age, gender, BMI, level of education etc. In chapter 5 the determinants are used for analyses.

To have a closer look at all 87 different exposure variable names, it is recommended to save all variables names in a separate file in your working directory. You can open this file and explore the different variable names.

```
write.table(colnames(HBM4EUData), file = "HeadingsHBM4EUData.csv",
           row.names=FALSE, na="", col.names=FALSE, sep=",")
```

During one of the steps in the analysis we will make use of pre-defined grouping of the variables. This is grouping done by prior knowledge, for example we know that `Hg` and `Cu` are both heavy metals. In theory the grouping could also be based on other (non-chemical) substance properties, for example the usage type or exposure route (occupational, diet etc). In this example based on the simulation data we will just use the chemical grouping, defined as `PFAS`, `PCBs&flame retardants`, `heavy metals`, `phenols` and `phthalates`. In the example the grouping will be used when plotting the data, with a different colour for each group.

The addition of the `group` to the variables needs to be done by hand and it is to be decided by the researcher which chemical belongs to which group. The definition of the groups can be added to the file with variable names which was saved in the working directory earlier:

1. Open the file `HeadingsHBM4EUData.csv` from your working directory
2. Add in the second column your defined group names
3. Groups can be defined by for example names (e.g. "flame retardants" or "phthalates")
4. Next, save the file as `HeadingsHBM4EUDataGroups.csv` in your working directory

```
Grouping <- read.csv("HeadingsHBM4EUDataGroups.csv", sep=";", header=FALSE)
Group <- as.vector(Grouping$V2) #usage of V2 since the columns were not assigned with
names
```

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5.3 Data preparation steps

Regarding data harmonisation the steps as described by WP10 will be followed. This means that all data follows the HBM4EU Data Template and variables will be coded following the HBM4EU Codebook. It is assumed that the data to be analysed is already harmonised and in the correct template (for the prioritised substances). From the mixture perspective within WP15 we need to perform some additional data preparation steps.

The data preparation steps are:

- Checking the distribution of the variables (also in WP10)
- Transforming the data if needed (also in WP10)
- Imputation of the data points below the LOD or LOQ (Limit of Detection or Limit of Quantification) (also in WP10)
- Correction for outliers
- Standardisation around zero
- Scaling of the data

In this document we need to go through all these data preparation steps. Imputation of data points below the LOD/LOQ within the script by WP10 is done by replacing all values below the LOD/LOQ by a constant value assuming the normal and the log-normal distribution of the observed percentiles. Since this will create a (larger) bias in the estimation of the correlation matrix, here an imputation using maximum likelihood estimation will be applied. This imputation method uses the available data to compute maximum likelihood estimates, giving unbiased estimates and standard errors.

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5.3.1 Data distribution

For many of the approaches described in this deliverable, an important assumption is that the variables are normally distributed. To check for normality, distribution plots can be created for each variable individually. It is important to have a closer look into all the individual variables to get a better feeling for the data. We show here an example for one variable ($PFOA$), showing the frequency, density and Q-Q plots for both the variable as-it-is (upper graphs) and transformed to a (natural)logarithmic scale (lower graphs). Median and standard deviations for both as-it-is and logarithmic scale are given as well.

```
Variable_selection <- "PFOA"
source("function_distribution.R")
description("distributions")
```



```
## [1] "median PFOA 1.07"
## [1] "standard deviation PFOA 2.14"
## [1] "median log PFOA 0.07"
## [1] "standard deviation log PFOA 1.02"
```

A histogram describes the frequency (counts) of the measurements in categories, a density plot is a parametric representation of the distribution of the biomarker measurement, finally a Q-Q (quantile-quantile) plot is a probability plot which describes if the data is normally distributed or not (when following the linear line the data is normally distributed). These plots will help to assess if the variables (of interest) can fulfil the first assumption of normality and which scaling methods suits best. In the example of $PFOA$ it is clear that the logarithmic scale suits best. Most likely HBM data is best described by a logarithmic transformation, however an individual assessment always needs to be made.

When opting for a transformation to the (natural) logarithmic scale, for example the following code could be used:

```
names <- colnames(HBM4EUData)
names <- colnames(HBM4EUData)[c(X,X)] # use this line to select column names
HBM4EUData[,paste0("log.",names)] <- log(HBM4EUData[,names])

log.name <- TRUE
if(log.name) {names <- paste0("log.",names)}
HBM4EUDataTrans <- HBM4EUData[,names]
```

The output of the transformation is within the dataset `HBM4EUDataTrans`.

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5.3.2 Imputation steps

Most statistical modelling techniques take as default only complete cases, as is the case when creating a correlation matrix. In Human Biomonitoring it is common that values are observed below the LOD/LOQ, resulting in a large percentage of missing values in the final dataset. To prevent bias due to missing data, we are going to apply some imputation techniques. In short, there are two different types of imputations needed within HBM data since missing values can be either:

- values below the LOD or LOQ
- data points which are missing from the dataset for some reason

Imputation below the LOD or LOQ is done based on the distribution of the values above the LOQ. Values between the LOD and LOQ will be imputed with a lower (LOD) and upper (LOQ) limit. Values below the LOD will be imputed between zero and the LOD value. Note that the LOD/LOQs might differ between the different variables, different laboratories and/or batches of measurements. The imputations run iteratively (several times) and are stratified per variable/laboratory/batch when having a different LOD/LOQ. As a rule of thumb the minimum amount of values which needs to be above the LOD is 30%. If less than 30% of the data for one variable is below the LOD, the variable needs to be excluded from the data analysis. Please note that when opted for a logarithmic transformation of your data, the LOD/LOQ also needs to be transformed.

```
agent.list <- colnames(HBM4EUDataTrans)
# for each variable on the list a LOD is allocated (example of 0.003).
# Note that the LOD needs also be transferred to a logarithmic scale
agent.LOD <- rep(log(0.003), length(agent.list))

# some variables might have a different LOD
# These can be specified seperately (e.g. the third variable has a LOD of 0.01)
agent.LOD[3] <- log(0.01)

source("imputationcode.R")
load("HBM4EUDataImputed1.RData")
```

Next, there might be missing values in the explanatory variables. The `mice` package will be applied to randomly impute the missing values. It will be explored what the best method is for imputation of missing exposure values above the LOD/LOQ.

```
imputed <- mice(HBM4EUDataImputed1)

HBM4EUDataImputed <- complete(imputed)
```

The `HBM4EUDataImputed` will be created here, based on the normally distributed data `HBM4EUDataTrans`.

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5.3.3 Outlier assessment

Data points are considered to be an outlier in this document when they are outside the 95th percentile. Outliers in the data might influence the correlation matrix, and therefore potentially also the network structure we are going to create in one of the next steps. For this reason, at first we want to check if there are any outliers (5% is outside the 95th percentile), and if an explanation could be found (laboratory analysis, fieldwork etcetera). This assessment needs to be made for each variable, which can be done by creating boxplots of the data. As a rule of thumb, we will place any outlier back on the limit of the 95th percentile, the effect of this will be analysed with sensitivity analysis when applying the methods on a real-dataset. The plot below will show the example variable `pcb31`, with one outlier in the left boxplot, which is placed back at the 95% percentile in the right boxplot.

5.3.4 Standardisation around zero and scaling

Standardisation around zero, or setting the median to zero, is one way to ‘improve’ the distribution of a variable. The other way is to scale the data, or in other words equalise the standard deviations. Both methods will help for comparison reasons between variables. The graph below shows the first 10 variables in our dataset being centred and scaled. In most statistical methods or R packages centring and scaling will be performed automatically.

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If you want to do this manually, the following code can be used for scaling and/or centring the data. The options `center` and `scale` can be turned on or off.

```
HBM4EUDataImputed2 <- as.data.frame(apply(HBM4EUDataImputed_adj, 2, function(x)
  { scale(x, center = TRUE, scale = TRUE) }))
```

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6 Describing mixtures of exposure

To recall the definition of mixtures used in this deliverable: ‘the common occurrence of chemical substances or their metabolites in the human body at a given time point’. We identify common occurrence in the HBM samples by creating a correlation matrix of the cleaned dataset based on the pairwise Pearson correlation between two variables. This matrix will also be saved to the working directory for further inspection. Correlation patterns will be described in two ways: using heatmaps and correlation globes or circos plots. The aim is to look into correlations between individual variables to check if there are patterns in the dataset.

```
CorHBM4EUData <- cor(HBM4EUDataImputed2)

write.csv(CorHBM4EUData, file="CorrelationMatrix_HBM4EUData.csv")
```

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6.1 Heatmaps

To get a first insight in correlation patterns, the correlation matrix is shown graphically by a heatmap, indicating patterns of negative and positive correlations. All positive correlations are coloured in blue (ranging from 0 to 1), negative correlations in red (from -1 to 0). The strength of correlation is reflected by the intensity of the colour. On the Y axis of the plot the a-priori defined groups (here: different chemical substance groups) are presented as different colours blocks, as indicated in the legend.

```
col<- colorRampPalette(c("red", "white", "blue")) heatmap.2(x=CorHBM4EUData,
col=col, density.info = "none", trace="none",
labCol=NA, labRow=NA, Rowv=F, Colv="Rowv", dendrogram = "none", symm=TRUE,
RowSideColors=my_colors, key.title = NA, margins=c(2,2), keysize=1.2,
main="Heatmap all variables")
legend(y=1.015, x=0.1,
legend= c("PCBs + BFRs", "heavy metals", "PFAS", "phenols", "phthalates"),
col=c("#1F78B4", "#B2DF8A", "#A6CEE3", "#33A02C", "#FB9A99"),lwd = 5, cex=0.5)
```


In our example we observe several blocks of highly, positively, correlated biomarker measurements (blue blocks). The patterns in the heatmap correspond to a certain degree to the colour blocks of the chemical grouping on the y-axis. Furthermore, several 'sub-groups' are detected within the originally defined chemical groups.

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As an example, we will zoom in on two a-priori defined chemical groups in the remainder of this document: 8 PCBs and 26 flame retardants. In the figure below the heatmap is zoomed in specifically to this subgroup.

```
heatmap.2(x=CorHBM4EUDataZoom, col=col, density.info = "none", trace="none",
  labRow=NA, Rowv=NA, Colv="Rowv", dendrogram="non", symm=TRUE,
  key.title=NA, keysize = 1.2,
  main="Heatmap PCBs and flame retardants")
```


Heatmap PCBs and flame retardants

In this graph we see three blocks of highly correlated (more intense colours) compounds existing within the subgroup of PCBs and flame retardants, while the correlation between compounds in each of these blocks to compounds in the two other blocks is absent (faded colours). Based on this visualisation a preliminary conclusion is that the compounds within these blocks share similar sources, while these sources are different between the blocks. We will continue by showing the common occurrence of chemicals (correlations) into other types of graphs.

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6.2 Correlation globes or circos plots

Besides showing the correlation in a heatmap, the correlation between two variables can also be plotted as a line between those variables. When all variables are presented in a circle we will call this a circos plot, or correlation globe. In this example the positive correlation between two variables is drawn as green lines, negative correlations as red lines. The stronger the correlation between two variables, the more intense the colour. In this plot only correlations above the absolute value of 0.3 are presented as lines, making the plot easier to interpret. The decision for such a minimum cut-off value depends largely on the input data and amount of variables included. Each variable is presented as a dot, or node, on the circular axis. The nodes are coloured according to the previously a priori defined chemical grouping. For the creation of this plot the package `qgraph` has been used, which offers many graphical options.

```
mycolors <- c(brewer.pal(name="Paired", n = 5)) # insert here the number of groups
defined par(mfrow=c(1,1))
qgraph(CorHBM4EUDData, graph="cor", layout="circle", bidirectional=TRUE,
       groups=Group, title="Circos plot of all variables and coloured by
       group",title.cex=1.2, color=mycolors, minimum=0.3,
       sampleSize=nrow(HBM4EUDDataImputed_adj), borders=FALSE, legend=TRUE,
       legend.cex=0.5, vsize=3, label.cex=1.2)
```

Circos plot of all variables and coloured by group

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Following the subgroup of PCBs and flame retardants, a separate circos plot can be created. An equal assumption has been made regarding the minimum cut-off value (0.3).

```
ggraph(CorHBM4EUDataZoom, graph="cor", layout="circle", bidirectional=TRUE,
  title="Circos plot PCBs and flame retardants", title.cex=1.5,
  color="#1F78B4", minimum=0.3, sampleSize=nrow(HBM4EUDataImputedZoom),
  borders=FALSE, legend= FALSE, vsize=6, label.cex=1.7)
```

Circos plot PCBs and flame retardants

While heatmaps are very useful to identify ‘highly correlated’ groups (or blocks), correlation globes help us to identify whether there are correlations ‘between groups’.

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6.3 Principal component analysis

In our example the simulated dataset consists of 87 exposure variables, of which some groups seem to be highly correlated, as seen in the heatmaps and circos plots. Underlying correlation structures can be used to calculate 'principal components' that reflect groups of biomarkers with a shared source or origin. Groups of correlated variables can be transformed to a (smaller) number of uncorrelated variables, called principal components. Principal Component Analysis (PCA) is a non-dependent procedure and a dimensionality reduction technique. PCA seeks a linear combination of variables such that the maximum variance is extracted from the variables. The first principal component accounts for as much of the variability in the data as possible, and each succeeding component accounts for as much of the remaining variability as possible. Principal components reflect both common and unique variance of the variables and may be seen as a variance-focused approach seeking to reproduce both the total variable variance with all components and to reproduce the correlations.

We will show some summary statistics of the principal component analysis:

```
pca.analysis <- prcomp(HBM4EUDataImputed2[,names])
pca_expr <- PCA(HBM4EUDataImputed2, graph=F)
```

The created element `pca_expr` includes all the components included in the results of the PCA. We can plot the variance explained by each component in a so-called scree plot (for the first 10 PCs see the plot below). We see that most of the variance in our data is explained by the first principal component, then the second, then the third and so on.

This can also be shown in a table, showing that the first 5 components explain 42% of the total variance in the dataset. After the first 5 components the additional variance explains does not increase largely.

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```
pca.analysis <- prcomp(HBM4EUDataImputed2[,names], center=TRUE, scale.=TRUE)
head(pca_expr$eig)
```

```
## eigenvalue percentage of variance cumulative percentage of variance
## comp 1 10.830511 12.448863 12.44886
## comp 2 8.711167 10.012836 22.46170
## comp 3 8.306429 9.547619 32.00932
## comp 4 5.900217 6.781859 38.79118
## comp 5 4.723306 5.429087 44.22026
## comp 6 4.140831 4.759576 48.97984
```

As mentioned above, with PCA correlation structures are used to identify groups of compounds that share a similar source or origin. In some cases it is possible to 'label' principal components based on the compounds that primarily contribute. We can gain insight into the primary contributors of a principal component by assessing the so-called loadings, which is the correlation between the original variables and the principal component (and which runs from 0 to 1). Squared factor loadings indicate what percentage of the variance in an original variable is explained by a factor. To facilitate the assessment of which factors are important contributors and which ones are not, we can apply an arbitrary cut-off. In our example we have used a threshold of 0.2 to identify important contributions, depending on the dataset the chosen threshold might differ. A total overview of the loadings from our example dataset is presented in the Annex. As an example, we see that principal component one appears to be dominated by trihalomethanes and bromides. Based on this observation we can label principal component 1 as such "trihalomethanes-bromides". We can use the principal components in further analyses where we try to identify determinants of exposure (section 7).

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6.4 Sparse Non-negative Matrix Under-approximation (SNMU) method

The SNMU method is based on a combination of the Sparse Non-negative Matrix Under-approximation (SNMU) with a clustering algorithm. The SNMU method is used in the first instance to characterise the main mixtures of substances and the overall exposure of the individuals to those mixtures. Then, a hierarchical clustering analysis is performed to identify clusters of the sampled population and their associated mixtures

6.4.1 SNMU method description

SNMU is a dimensionality reduction technique based on a combination of different pre-existing methods to meet positivity and sparsity criteria needed to obtain interpretable results, to determine mixtures of substances and clusters of individuals [1][2][3]. The main algorithm is the Non-negative Matrix Factorization (NMF), the matrix M is factorized into two matrixes U and V with the property that all three matrixes have no negative elements [4]. The non-negativity property is well adapted to the used dataset.

Figure 1: Illustration of approximate non-negative matrix factorization of the matrix M using one dimension for u and v .

The approximation of M by $u \times v$ is achieved by minimising an error function while being subject to positivity and under-approximation constraints. This is an optimisation problem, which is proposed to be solved by Lee and Seung using a multiplicative update rule adding a sparsity coefficient [5]. The SNMU algorithm combines the one dimensional NMF with sparsity and under-approximation constraints successively to obtain multiples vectors u and v that are in this case vectors, then those multiples vectors (u_i) and (v_i) are gathered together to create two new matrixes U and V :

$$U = (u_1 | u_2 | \dots | u_n) \quad V = \begin{pmatrix} v_1 \\ v_2 \\ \vdots \\ v_n \end{pmatrix}$$

N is the number of times the NMF is repeated and will give the number of mixtures in our case study. Choosing an adequate number n is thus important, and can be optimised using specific method detailed further. The NMF has an inherent selection property, and with the sparsity constraints this property is more prominent and visible.

6.4.1.1 SNMU step by step

1st step:

Formatting the dataset to obtain a matrix where the substances are in rows, the samples/individuals are in columns and the values inside the matrix are positive.

2nd step:

Applying the one dimensional NMF with sparsity and under-approximation constraints:

Figure 2: Illustration of NMF decomposition

Where $u_1 > 0$, $v_1 > 0$ and $M - u_1 \times v_1 > 0$

3rd step:

Applying the NMF again but on the error matrix $M - u_1 \times v_1$

Figure 3: Illustration of a SNMU step

Where $u_2 > 0$, $v_2 > 0$ and $M - u_1 \times v_1 - u_2 \times v_2 > 0$

4th step:

3rd step is repeated n-2 times so that n pairs of vectors (u_i, v_i) are created.

5th step:

(u_i) and (v_i) are gathered to create two new matrixes U and V

Example of results using N=4 mixtures:

Figure 4: Illustration of the SNMU results

6.4.1.2 Number of mixtures N

For each new mixture the SNMU calculates the residual sum of squares (RMSE). Once plotted as a function of N a descending trend can be observed. One method to define N is to visually search the highest decrease of the RMSE on the curve (an example of graphical solution: Zetlaoui et al. 2011 [6]). However it is difficult to interpret and compare the different inflexion on the curve, to do so a measure of the angle (DR_{RMSE}) is plotted as a function of N.

Thus to better determine the optimal number of mixtures, we propose to calculate for each possible number of mixture i the ratio between each consecutive RMSE, that result is then noted $DR_{RMSE}(i)$:

$$DR_{RMSE}(i) = \frac{RMSE(i)}{RMSE(i-1)} - \frac{RMSE(i-1)}{RMSE(i-2)} \text{ for } i \text{ a number of mixtures.}$$

The plot of this ratio against the number of mixtures i indicates the optimal numbers of mixtures to be used for the clustering method.

6.4.1.3 Clustering of the population

To cluster individuals in groups with similar exposure to the different mixtures, the divisive hierarchical cluster analysis (DHCA) is applied on the matrix V obtained from the SNMU. Results of the DHCA can be presented in a dendrogram which makes it possible to see how the population is divided. The number of population clusters is chosen by searching the longest jump between two levels in the dendrogram.

Figure 5: Dendrogram of the V matrix with 3 population clusters represented by the red, green and blue coloured boxes

6.4.1.4 Comparison between the clusters and the global population exposures and determinants of exposure

Once the divisive hierarchical cluster analysis is used and the population clusters are identified, it becomes interesting to compare the differences between these clusters and the whole population. Student's tests were used to determine the substances composing the mixtures for which the difference between the exposure of one particular population cluster and that of the whole population is significant. This method highlights those individual population clusters and mixtures with higher and lower exposure comparing to the whole population.

Cluster Results 1 , 984 individuals

Main mixtures	Main substances	Cluster	Mean	Standard deviation	Population	Mean	Standard deviation	Comparison
Mixtures 4 (17.4%)	ITHM_preg (11.2 %)	984 individuals	2.35	4.46	1200 individuals	10.2	42.9	*** (<)
	IBROM_preg (11.1 %)		2.45	4.93		10.9	48.2	*** (<)
	IBROM_T2 (10.8 %)		2.68	6.34		11.1	49.5	*** (<)
	ITHM_T3 (10.7 %)		2.44	5.2		10	37.1	*** (<)

Figure 6: Comparison table of the level of exposure between clusters and the total population

Comparison column: * corresponds to a significant difference between averages according to a t-test : * si p-value<0.05, ** if p-value<0.01, *** if p-value<0.001, (<) if Mean Cluster < Mean Population, (>) if Mean Cluster > Mean Population

Student's tests were also done to determine potential determinants of the exposure clusters regarding the variables PM25_T, Ben_preg, SUGAR and ALCO (see section 7, impact of determinants).

6.4.2 SNMU method applied on the simulated dataset

6.4.2.1 Number of mixtures

We started the algorithm using $N=12$. Using four or ten mixtures gives the highest reduction of the RMSE. Regarding cluster analysis we found that ten mixtures give the best interpretation of the results. Thus, ten mixtures are used to obtain the following results. As an extra check, we also started the algorithm using $N=20$ which results in the same optimal number of mixtures.

Best number of mixtures 4 10 2 9

Figure 7: Plot of the difference of the residual mean square error ratios as a function of the number N of mixtures

The SNMU combined with the divisive hierarchical cluster analysis lead to 3 clusters of individuals and their exposure to each of the 10 mixtures.

Figure 8: Dendrogram representation of the clustering

6.4.2.2 Composition of mixtures

The 10 mixtures explain 65.8% of the variance of the original HBM dataset. The Figures 9-10-11 present the composition of the 10 mixtures. The substances with a weight inferior to 1% are not displayed in the tables. The mixture 1 is mainly composed of flame retardants. The mixture 2 is composed of substances from different families: flame retardants, heavy metals, phenols, one phthalate, one PCB and the PFHxS. The mixture 3 is composed of perfluorinated compounds and phenols. Heavy metals composed the mixture 4. The mixture 5 contains phthalates and heavy metals. The mixture 6 is mainly composed of PCBs and heavy metals. The mixture 7 is composed of phenols and phthalates. The mixture 8 and 10 are composed of flame retardants, phthalates and heavy metals. The mixture 9 contains, flame retardants, heavy metals, perfluorinated compounds and BPA.

Mixtures 1 Explained variance = 18,9 %		Mixtures 2 Explained variance = 12,9 %		Mixtures 3 Explained variance = 8,1 %		Mixtures 4 Explained variance = 9,1 %	
Compound	Weight	Compound	Weight	Compound	Weight	Compound	Weight
THM_0	5,6 %	bde47	5,5 %	mPFNA	7,3 %	Cd_3	5,9 %
THM_1	5,4 %	bde99	5,4 %	PFNA	7,2 %	Cu_3	5,1 %
THM_2	5,4 %	bde28	5,1 %	mPFOA	7,2 %	TI_3	4,8 %
THM_3	5,4 %	bde71	4,8 %	PFOA	6,9 %	Cu_1	4,6 %
BROM_0	5,3 %	bde66	4,7 %	mPFHxS	6,7 %	Co_3	4,6 %
BROM_1	5,2 %	bde209	4,7 %	mPFOS	6,4 %	Cs_3	4,5 %
BROM_3	5,2 %	bde17	4,6 %	PFHxS	5,5 %	Cd_1	4 %
BROM_2	5,1 %	bde138	4,5 %	ePB	5,5 %	Se_3	4 %
CHCL3_0	3,3 %	bde100	4,2 %	PFOS	5,3 %	Pb_3	4 %
CHCL3_1	2,8 %	bde154	4,2 %	TCS	4,2 %	Zn_3	3,9 %
CHCL3_3	2,8 %	bde153	4 %	pcb180	3,3 %	TI_1	3,7 %
CHCL3_2	2,7 %	DCP24	3,3 %	pPB	2,3 %	Sb_3	3,7 %
PFOA	1,1 %	bde85	3,2 %	pcb118	2,1 %	Ni_3	3,4 %
TI_3	1 %	bde183	2,9 %	pcb153	2,1 %	Sb_1	3,1 %
		DCP25	2,9 %	Cd_1	1,9 %	Co_1	3 %
		Se_3	2,4 %	pcb138	1,8 %	Mo_1	3 %
		bde190	2,2 %	mPB	1,8 %	Mo_3	2,8 %
		pb	1,5 %	pcb18	1,7 %	Zn_1	2,4 %
		mPB	1,4 %	Mo_3	1,6 %	Pb_1	2,4 %
		pPB	1,3 %	BP	1,6 %	Ni_1	2,2 %
		PFHxS	1,2 %	bde138	1,5 %	BP	2,1 %
		pcb31	1,1 %	hg	1,5 %	Se_1	2 %
		hg	1,1 %	Cd_3	1,5 %	7ohMMeOP	2 %
		Cu_3	1,1 %	pcb56	1,4 %	pb	1,9 %
		MnBP	1,1 %	7ohMMeOP	1,3 %	As_3	1,9 %
		Zn_3	1 %	Sb_3	1,2 %	Cs_1	1,6 %
		bPB	1 %			bPB	1,5 %
						pcb84	1,2 %

Figure 9: Mixtures 1-4 composition

Among the 87 initial substances, only the ones with a weight superior to 1% are displayed

Mixtures 5		Mixtures 6		Mixtures 7		Mixtures 8	
Explained variance = 4,4 %		Explained variance = 3,2 %		Explained variance = 2,2 %		Explained variance = 2 %	
Compound	Weight	Compound	Weight	Compound	Weight	Compound	Weight
MEOHP	18 %	pcb153	24 %	pPB	23,1 %	CHCL3_2	24,5 %
MEHHP	17,5 %	pcb138	21,7 %	mPB	22,4 %	CHCL3_0	24,2 %
5cxMEPP	16,1 %	pcb180	20,8 %	2cxMMHP	6,7 %	CHCL3_3	17,7 %
MEHP	11,6 %	pcb56	10 %	7ohMMeOP	6,5 %	CHCL3_1	14,1 %
2cxMMHP	8,9 %	pcb84	8,2 %	ePB	6,4 %	hg	5,2 %
7ohMMeOP	3,7 %	pcb31	2,4 %	bPB	5,6 %	As_3	3,5 %
Ni_1	1,6 %	pcb118	1,6 %	MiBP	3 %	bde47	1,3 %
MiBP	1,5 %	bPB	1,2 %	MnBP	3 %	MEP	1,3 %
Sb_1	1,3 %	PFOS	1 %	Cu_1	2,1 %	MiBP	1,1 %
MBzP	1,3 %			Mo_3	2 %		
Mo_1	1,2 %			Co_1	1,7 %		
Cs_1	1,2 %			Cd_1	1,6 %		
Pb_1	1,2 %			MBzP	1,6 %		
MnBP	1,2 %			bde66	1,3 %		
				bde138	1,3 %		
				bde209	1,2 %		
				DCP24	1,2 %		
				5cxMEPP	1,2 %		
				pcb180	1,1 %		
				Ni_3	1,1 %		

Figure 10: Mixtures 5-8 composition

Among the 87 initial substances, only the ones with a weight superior to 1% are displayed

Mixtures 9 Explained variance = 2,3 %		Mixtures 10 Explained variance = 2,7 %	
Compound	Weight	Compound	Weight
As_3	16,9 %	Cs_1	14,4 %
As_1	16,2 %	Tl_1	11,2 %
hg	14,7 %	Co_1	11 %
PFOS	9,1 %	Ni_1	9,8 %
mPFOS	6,8 %	Mo_1	9,4 %
BPA	6,6 %	Pb_1	6,4 %
Pb_1	5 %	Cu_1	6,3 %
Ni_1	2,3 %	Cd_1	4,4 %
bde66	1,8 %	Zn_1	4 %
pcb56	1,7 %	Sb_1	3,9 %
Se_1	1,5 %	MEP	3,9 %
CHCL3_3	1,4 %	MEHP	2,3 %
Se_3	1,4 %	Se_1	2,2 %
Sb_1	1,2 %	CHCL3_3	1,5 %
Sb_3	1 %	bde183	1,1 %
TI_3	1 %	bde100	1 %

Figure 11: Mixtures 9-10 composition

Among the 87 initial substances, only the ones with a weight superior to 1% are displayed

The truncated heatmap in the figure below presents the weight of each substance in each of the ten mixtures. Only the first 23 substances are shown as an example of result produced by the SNMU. A weight closed to 0 means that the substance is not important in the mixture and a weight closed to 1 indicates that the substance plays a major role in the mixture.

Figure 12: Truncated heatmap of the 10 mixtures (showing only 23 of the 87 substances)

6.4.2.3 Cluster exposure descriptions

Only the mixtures with the highest contribution (% of exposure) are detailed in tables and until the sum of their contributions reach at least 50% of the total cluster exposure. Cluster 2 is presented here; the results of clusters 1 and 3 are presented in the Annex.

Cluster 2, 297 individuals

The second cluster is composed of 297 individuals. Mixtures 6 and 4 make up for more than 30% of the cluster exposure. The mixtures 1, 5 and 10 each contribute to around 10% of the cluster exposure. The cluster's main characteristic is that the exposure is significantly higher compared to the global population for a majority of substances of the mixtures 6, 4, 5 and 10 and lower for the flame retardant compounds composing the mixture 1.

Figure 18: Importance of the 10 mixtures in cluster 2 exposure

		Cluster 2			Global population			
Mixture 6	Substances	Mean	Standard.deviation	P95	Mean	Standard.deviation	P95	Comparison
PCBs	pcb153 (24 %)	2.96	2.89	8.59	1.6	1.94	4.95	*** (>)
PCBs	pcb138 (21.7 %)	2.81	3.09	7.28	1.56	1.96	4.89	*** (>)
PCBs	pcb180 (20.8 %)	2.84	2.78	7.39	1.56	1.85	5.02	*** (>)
PCBs	pcb56 (9.97 %)	2.76	3.12	8.76	1.73	2.21	5.54	*** (>)
PCBs	pcb84 (8.2 %)	2.65	2.76	7.39	1.67	2.03	5.87	*** (>)
PCBs	pcb31 (2.4 %)	1.88	2.17	5.55	1.52	1.96	4.93	* (>)
PCBs	pcb118 (1.62 %)	1.96	2.45	6.29	1.58	2.11	4.71	* (>)
phenols	bPB (1.16 %)	1.86	2.21	5.48	1.43	1.71	4.43	** (>)
PFAS	PFOS (0.988 %)	1.94	2.49	5.58	1.69	2.16	5.3	
flame retardants	bde183 (0.859 %)	1.82	2.34	5.25	1.53	1.86	4.57	* (>)
heavy metal	Pb_3 (0.762 %)	2.2	3.88	7.12	1.7	2.53	5.32	* (>)
heavy metal	Sb_1 (0.725 %)	2.32	2.77	7.21	1.64	2.05	5.35	*** (>)
flame retardants	bde154 (0.668 %)	1.65	2.04	4.8	1.76	2.52	5.58	
flame retardants	bde153 (0.583 %)	1.56	1.92	4.41	1.71	2.44	5.14	
flame retardants	bde190 (0.551 %)	1.78	2.4	5.79	1.59	2.16	4.81	
heavy metal	pb (0.534 %)	1.92	2.82	5.21	1.64	2.23	4.88	
heavy metal	Pb_1 (0.484 %)	2.2	2.47	6.73	1.62	2	5.11	*** (>)

Figure 19: Cluster 2 exposure to mixture 6 (19.4% of the total cluster exposure) and comparison with the global population

Comparison column: * corresponds to a significant difference between averages according to a t-test: * si p-value<0.05, ** if p-value<0.01, *** if p-value<0.001, (<) if Mean Cluster < Mean Population, (>) if Mean Cluster > Mean Population

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Mixture 4	Substances	Cluster 2			Global population			Comparison
		Mean	Standard.deviation	P95	Mean	Standard.deviation	P95	
heavy metal	Cu_3 (5.13 %)	2.03	3.35	6.97	1.67	2.27	5.08	
heavy metal	Tl_3 (4.83 %)	1.72	2.24	5.45	1.53	1.87	4.5	
heavy metal	Co_3 (4.59 %)	2.07	2.6	6.13	1.68	2.14	5.27	* (>)
heavy metal	Cu_1 (4.56 %)	2.64	2.97	8.25	1.61	2.01	5.08	*** (>)
heavy metal	Cs_3 (4.46 %)	2.03	2.54	6.14	1.58	1.89	5.17	** (>)
heavy metal	Pb_3 (4.02 %)	2.2	3.88	7.12	1.7	2.53	5.32	* (>)
heavy metal	Cd_1 (3.97 %)	2.59	2.9	7.97	1.66	2.22	5.67	*** (>)
heavy metal	Se_3 (3.96 %)	1.85	2.08	5.63	1.53	1.78	4.57	* (>)
heavy metal	Zn_3 (3.88 %)	1.92	2.37	6.15	1.67	1.93	5.47	
heavy metal	Tl_1 (3.67 %)	2.52	2.97	8.32	1.59	2.01	4.9	*** (>)
heavy metal	Sb_3 (3.66 %)	2.05	2.94	6.43	1.75	2.6	5.12	
heavy metal	Ni_3 (3.36 %)	2.06	2.91	5.81	1.7	2.19	5.16	* (>)
heavy metal	Sb_1 (3.14 %)	2.32	2.77	7.21	1.64	2.05	5.35	*** (>)
heavy metal	Co_1 (3.03 %)	2.6	2.83	8.02	1.67	1.98	5.12	*** (>)
heavy metal	Mo_1 (2.95 %)	2.73	3.44	8.57	1.66	2.25	5.42	*** (>)
heavy metal	Mo_3 (2.83 %)	1.88	2.39	6.17	1.68	2.2	5.42	
heavy metal	Pb_1 (2.41 %)	2.2	2.47	6.73	1.62	2	5.11	*** (>)
heavy metal	Zn_1 (2.4 %)	2.49	4.41	8.34	1.79	2.83	5.48	* (>)
heavy metal	Ni_1 (2.17 %)	2.75	2.94	8.44	1.8	2.33	6.51	*** (>)
phenols	BP (2.11 %)	1.73	1.7	4.8	1.64	1.94	5.31	
phthalates	7ohMMeOP (2.01 %)	2.27	3.04	7.71	1.71	2.06	5.31	** (>)
heavy metal	Se_1 (2.01 %)	2.67	6.11	7.36	1.67	3.35	4.97	** (>)
heavy metal	pb (1.92 %)	1.92	2.82	5.21	1.64	2.23	4.88	
heavy metal	As_3 (1.88 %)	1.62	1.96	5.55	1.72	2.31	6.06	
heavy metal	Cs_1 (1.56 %)	2.7	4.39	7.41	1.62	2.59	5.44	*** (>)
phenols	bPB (1.51 %)	1.86	2.21	5.48	1.43	1.71	4.43	** (>)
PCBs	pcb84 (1.22 %)	2.65	2.76	7.39	1.67	2.03	5.87	*** (>)

Figure 20: Cluster 2 exposure to mixture 4 (12.5% of the total cluster exposure) and comparison with the global population

Comparison column: * corresponds to a significant difference between averages according to a t-test: * si p-value<0.05, ** if p-value<0.01, *** if p-value<0.001, (<) if Mean Cluster < Mean Population, (>) if Mean Cluster > Mean Population

Mixture 1	Substances	Cluster 2			Global population			Comparison
		Mean	Standard.deviation	P95	Mean	Standard.deviation	P95	
flame retardants	THM_3 (5.44 %)	1.12	1.08	3.1	1.59	1.85	5.29	*** (<)
flame retardants	THM_2 (5.37 %)	1.14	1.07	3.22	1.59	1.91	4.98	*** (<)
flame retardants	THM_1 (5.35 %)	1.11	1.09	2.94	1.58	1.88	5.28	*** (<)
flame retardants	BROM_0 (5.32 %)	1.16	1.16	3.27	1.61	1.92	5.18	*** (<)
flame retardants	BROM_3 (5.24 %)	1.15	1.14	3.25	1.61	1.9	5.16	*** (<)
flame retardants	BROM_1 (5.18 %)	1.16	1.18	3.29	1.6	1.93	5.15	*** (<)
flame retardants	BROM_2 (5.14 %)	1.18	1.2	3.13	1.61	1.94	5.21	*** (<)
flame retardants	CHCL3_0 (3.32 %)	1.04	0.973	2.71	1.51	1.69	4.64	*** (<)
flame retardants	CHCL3_1 (2.8 %)	1.02	0.995	3.16	1.52	1.72	4.72	*** (<)
flame retardants	CHCL3_3 (2.79 %)	1.2	1.24	3.45	1.51	1.71	4.42	*** (<)
flame retardants	CHCL3_2 (2.7 %)	1.08	0.947	3	1.55	1.82	5.09	*** (<)
PFAS	PFOA (1.12 %)	1.66	2.14	4.93	1.74	2.14	5.42	
heavy metal	Tl_3 (1 %)	1.72	2.24	5.45	1.53	1.87	4.5	

Figure 21: Cluster 2 exposure to mixture 1 (11.7% of the total cluster exposure) and comparison with the global population

Comparison column: * corresponds to a significant difference between averages according to a t-test: * si p-value<0.05, ** if p-value<0.01, *** if p-value<0.001, (<) if Mean Cluster < Mean Population, (>) if Mean Cluster > Mean Population

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Mixture 5	Substances	Cluster 2			Global population			Comparison
		Mean	Standard.deviation	P95	Mean	Standard.deviation	P95	
phthalates	MEHHP (17.5 %)	2.53	4.6	9.85	1.61	2.58	4.83	*** (>)
phthalates	5cxMEPP (16.1 %)	2.32	3.13	8.48	1.58	1.99	5.23	*** (>)
phthalates	MEHP (11.6 %)	2.29	3.24	7.84	1.56	2.14	4.71	*** (>)
phthalates	2cxMMHP (8.92 %)	2.42	4.06	7.73	1.61	2.43	4.85	** (>)
phthalates	7ohMMeOP (3.73 %)	2.27	3.04	7.71	1.71	2.06	5.31	** (>)
heavy metal	Ni_1 (1.63 %)	2.75	2.94	8.44	1.8	2.33	6.51	*** (>)
phthalates	MiBP (1.51 %)	1.96	4.05	5.12	1.7	2.6	5.11	
heavy metal	Sb_1 (1.31 %)	2.32	2.77	7.21	1.64	2.05	5.35	*** (>)
phthalates	MBzP (1.26 %)	2.04	2.65	7.53	1.74	2.24	6	
heavy metal	Pb_1 (1.25 %)	2.2	2.47	6.73	1.62	2	5.11	*** (>)
heavy metal	Cs_1 (1.21 %)	2.7	4.39	7.41	1.62	2.59	5.44	*** (>)
phthalates	MnBP (1.17 %)	1.88	2.55	6.2	1.71	2.21	5.39	
heavy metal	Mo_1 (1.17 %)	2.73	3.44	8.57	1.66	2.25	5.42	*** (>)
heavy metal	As_1 (0.925 %)	1.84	1.99	5.23	1.62	2.06	4.76	
heavy metal	As_3 (0.911 %)	1.62	1.96	5.55	1.72	2.31	6.06	
phenols	BPA (0.881 %)	1.65	1.8	5.01	1.63	2.24	5.3	

Figure 22: Cluster 2 exposure to mixture 5 (11 % of the total cluster exposure) and comparison with the global population

Comparison column: * corresponds to a significant difference between averages according to a t-test: * si p-value<0.05, ** if p-value<0.01, *** if p-value<0.001, (<) if Mean Cluster < Mean Population, (>) if Mean Cluster > Mean Population

6.4.3 Code for SNMU algorithm

The R code used for running the SNMU algorithm and creating the associated graphics and tables is detailed in the Annex.

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6.5 Network analysis

While correlation matrix-based methods as described above provide a useful first description of the structure of the data, there is a possibility that using pairwise correlation coefficients will give misleading results if there is another, confounding, variable that is numerically related to both variables of interest. We can control for this potential bias by correcting pairwise correlations for potential confounding factors by computing the partial correlation coefficient. While such corrections are straightforward in the case of 3 potentially confounding biomarkers, scaling to large sets of biomarker data is challenging. This is the domain of network analysis. Network analysis can be used to see which nodes/variables are connected, what the structure is between nodes and if there are any central or network driving variables.

Our goal is to estimate the best undirected graph on the variables. ‘Undirected graphs’ is an approach to describe the conditional independence among many variables. Meaning that two variables are correlated given the other variables. In a such a graph, a line (edge) between two variables (nodes) implies that the variables are partially dependent (as is, smaller or greater than zero). For the network analysis we will make use of the package `huge` to conduct graph estimation. In this graphical modelling we will only focus on the a priori defined chemical groups ‘PCBs’ and ‘flame retardants’, making the graphical outcomes easier to interpret.

6.5.1 Optimal graph identification

To construct an optimal network in our data we start with defining the so called graph-path, which is estimated based the partial correlation between all variables (biomarkers) in our data. Lines (edges) between the nodes in the networks (the biomarkers) indicate partial correlation. Positive partial correlations will be drawn as black lines, negative partial correlations as red lines.

```
mb = huge(as.matrix(HBM4EUDataImputedZoom))
```

As a second step the method finds a balance between the complexity of the network and its capacity to explain the variability in the biomarker dataset using a so-called regularisation parameter. Different choices for regularisation parameters are available, in this example we use “stars”.

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```

StARS_analysis <- huge.select(mb, criterion ="stars", verbose = FALSE)

#gr.glasso<- graph.adjacency(StARS_analysis$refit)
#V(gr.glasso)$label.cex <- NA
#V(gr.glasso)$color <- rep(c("blue","red"))
#plot(gr.glasso, vertex.size=10, edge.arrow.mode="-")

par(mfrow=c(1,1))
A <- StARS_analysis$refit
colnames(A) <- rownames(A) <- colnames(HBM4EUDataImputedZoom)
DataSet <- graph_from_adjacency_matrix(A, mode = "undirected")
plot(DataSet)

```


The outcome of this approach is the graphical presentation of the underlying network structure in our biomarker data, striking a balance between complexity and explaining power.

6.5.2 Community detection

After the creation of the optimal network in our biomarker data we can explore whether groups of particular highly correlated biomarkers exist within the network (also called communities). Such communities can provide insight into the existence of natural groupings; e.g. based on chemical structure (e.g. all PCBs group together), however they can also demonstrate the existence of communities that exist of multiple chemical groups. Within the network of the subgroup different communities are detected, which are presented by different colours in the graph.

We observe that the bromated compounds (starting with BROM_) cluster together with the trihalomethanes and chloroform, while PCBs and PBDE's are identified to be part of another cluster. Furthermore, we observe that two communities are detected within the group of PBDE's, potentially indicating different origin or sources. Interesting are also the negative relations between the networks of PCBs and PBDE's, indicated with red lines.

```
plot(cluster_fast_greedy(DataSet), DataSet,
      main="Network PCBs and flame retardants")
```

Network PCBs and flame retardants

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7 Impact of determinants on mixtures

7.1 Determinants considered

The minimal set of determinants that will be included in the final data analysis on existing HBM data will include country, region (including rural and urban), sampling period, socio-economic status, gender, BMI, and age (or year born to look at cohort effects). Additional determinants will be included based on their availability (as indicated in the inventory in WP7 and priority group specific inventories that have been conducted in WP10, Task 10.3-10.4). Special interest is in those additional variables, which might distinguish patterns of exposure.

To further dive into the explanation of the combinations of exposure concentrations (structure of the networks, the loadings of the principal components, clusters of the SNMU method), we will make use of so-called determinants, called `PM25_T`, `Ben_preg`, `SUGAR` and `ALCO` in this document. Where `SUGAR` refers to the daily sugar intake and `ALCO` to alcohol consumption. Note that all the determinants and data used for this document is based on simulated data! The term determinant is used for an explanatory factor of the exposure values, for example region/country, age, gender, BMI, lifestyle factors etc.

Just as for the variables in the dataset we can check for multicollinearity (high correlations) between determinants with a correlation matrix.

```
cor (Det)
```

```
##          PM25_T    Ben_preg    SUGAR    ALCO
## PM25_T    1.00000000  0.43622450 -0.00575079  0.08740326
## Ben_preg  0.43622450  1.00000000 -0.01292401  0.08504929
## SUGAR    -0.00575079 -0.01292401  1.00000000  0.04292049
## ALCO     0.08740326  0.08504929  0.04292049  1.00000000
```

No high correlations between determinants were observed in our example, indicating non-common sources.

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7.2 Principal component regression

Principal component regression is conducted by creating a regression model using the first (few) dimension reduced principal components. Principal components are modelled with determinants, or explaining variables, by creating a regression model with the component(s) as outcome variable(s). Here we show two models, first with only the first principal component, and secondly with the first three principal components.

```
#note that SUGAR is also on a log scale
LM_pc1 <- lm(pca.analysis$x[, 1] ~ SUGAR)

summary(LM_pc1)

##
## Call:
## lm(formula = pca.analysis$x[, 1] ~ SUGAR)
##
## Residuals:
##      Min       1Q   Median       3Q      Max
## -6.3518 -1.2902 -0.0296  1.2503  6.0764
##
## Coefficients:
##              Estimate Std. Error t value Pr(>|t|)
## (Intercept) -0.005296  0.054787  -0.097  0.923
## SUGAR        0.297020  0.055284   5.373 9.32e-08 ***
## ---
## Signif. codes:  0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1
##
## Residual standard error: 1.898 on 1198 degrees of freedom
## Multiple R-squared:  0.02353, Adjusted R-squared:  0.02271
## F-statistic: 28.86 on 1 and 1198 DF, p-value: 9.318e-08
```

The first model shows that the third determinant SUGAR has a significant effect on the first Principal component. As described in section 6.3, principal component one was dominated by trihalomethanes and bromides and labelled as “trihalomethanes-bromides”, explaining 12% of the total variation in the dataset. We can interpret this as the correlation between trihalomethanes-bromides being related to daily sugar intake.

Additional models could be run for the first five principal components (with PCA it was shown that the first 5 PCs were explaining ~44% of the variation in the dataset) and for different determinants. The models below show the effect of the four determinants on the first three PCs (resulting in separate ‘Responses’ for each PCs). Ideally potential determinants would be tested in multiple regression models, which in our case provide similar inferences as the univariate models.

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#note that the determinants are also on a log scale

```
LM2_pc10 <- lm(pca.analysis$x[,1:3] ~ PM25_T+Ben_preg+SUGAR+ALCO)
```

```
summary(LM2_pc10)
```

```
## Response PC1 :
##
## Call:
## lm(formula = PC1 ~ PM25_T + Ben_preg + SUGAR + ALCO)
##
## Residuals:
##      Min       1Q   Median       3Q      Max
## -6.2747 -1.3116 -0.0407  1.2390  6.0184
##
## Coefficients:
##              Estimate Std. Error t value Pr(>|t|)
## (Intercept) -0.006623   0.054774  -0.121   0.9038
## PM25_T      -0.104034   0.060439  -1.721   0.0855 .
## Ben_preg     0.079385   0.060731   1.307   0.1914
## SUGAR        0.300626   0.055291   5.437 6.56e-08 ***
## ALCO        -0.073198   0.054969  -1.332   0.1832
## ---
## Signif. codes:  0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1
##
## Residual standard error: 1.896 on 1195 degrees of freedom
## Multiple R-squared:  0.02781,    Adjusted R-squared:  0.02456
## F-statistic: 8.546 on 4 and 1195 DF,  p-value: 8.459e-07
##
##
## Response PC2 :
##
## Call:
## lm(formula = PC2 ~ PM25_T + Ben_preg + SUGAR + ALCO)
##
## Residuals:
##      Min       1Q   Median       3Q      Max
## -4.6376 -0.8765 -0.0340  0.9075  4.2860
##
## Coefficients:
##              Estimate Std. Error t value Pr(>|t|)
## (Intercept)  0.0009185  0.0371980   0.025   0.9803
## PM25_T       0.0715191  0.0410454   1.742   0.0817 .
## Ben_preg    -0.0230632  0.0412436  -0.559   0.5761
## SUGAR        0.0923878  0.0375493   2.460   0.0140 *
## ALCO         0.0839130  0.0373306   2.248   0.0248 *
## ---
## Signif. codes:  0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1
##
## Residual standard error: 1.287 on 1195 degrees of freedom
## Multiple R-squared:  0.01262,    Adjusted R-squared:  0.009311
## F-statistic: 3.817 on 4 and 1195 DF,  p-value: 0.004334
##
##
## Response PC3 :
##
## Call:
## lm(formula = PC3 ~ PM25_T + Ben_preg + SUGAR + ALCO)
##
## Residuals:
```

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```
##      Min      1Q  Median      3Q      Max
## -3.9761 -0.8664 0.0460  0.8403  4.0537
##
## Coefficients:
##              Estimate Std. Error t value Pr(>|t|)
## (Intercept)  0.004494   0.035331   0.127   0.899
## PM25_T      0.011061   0.038985   0.284   0.777
## Ben_preg    -0.003460   0.039173  -0.088   0.930
## SUGAR       -0.205721   0.035664  -5.768 1.02e-08 ***
## ALCO        0.033668   0.035457   0.950   0.343
## ---
## Signif. codes:  0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1
##
## Residual standard error: 1.223 on 1195 degrees of freedom
## Multiple R-squared:  0.02759,    Adjusted R-squared:  0.02434
## F-statistic: 8.477 on 4 and 1195 DF,  p-value: 9.598e-07
```

7.3 Cluster analysis of the SNMU approach results

No significant difference between the values of the whole population and the clusters can be observed except for the cluster 3 which has a significantly higher mean value for the characteristic Sugar. Thus, the clusters do not appear to be determined by the variables ALCO, PM25_T or ben_preg.

ALCO											
	Mean	Standard deviation	Min	P05	P25	P50	P75	P90	P95	P99	Max
Global population	1,63	2,04	0,06	0,18	0,49	0,95	1,95	3,66	5,39	10,61	20,72
Cluster 1	1,60	2,00	0,06	0,19	0,49	0,94	1,86	3,85	5,57	10,40	20,72
Cluster 2	1,57	1,89	0,10	0,19	0,52	0,95	1,87	3,40	5,07	9,48	17,68
Cluster 3	1,78	2,36	0,06	0,15	0,45	1,03	2,26	3,59	4,74	12,21	19,15
pm25_T											
	Mean	Standard deviation	Min	P05	P25	P50	P75	P90	P95	P99	Max
Global population	1,67	2,64	0,04	0,17	0,51	0,95	1,92	3,48	5,25	11,04	40,19
Cluster 1	1,75	2,75	0,05	0,16	0,53	0,97	1,97	3,74	5,49	11,05	39,80
Cluster 2	1,57	2,84	0,07	0,19	0,50	0,87	1,68	3,16	4,81	10,30	40,19
Cluster 3	1,56	1,81	0,04	0,19	0,51	0,99	2,09	2,91	4,47	8,75	14,76
Sugar											
	Mean	Standard deviation	Min	P05	P25	P50	P75	P90	P95	P99	Max
Global population	1,63	1,88	0,06	0,20	0,53	1,04	2,06	3,51	4,90	10,49	19,92
Cluster 1	1,67	2,00	0,06	0,20	0,51	1,02	2,07	3,58	5,19	11,38	19,92
Cluster 2	1,45	1,55	0,07	0,19	0,47	1,01	1,81	3,12	4,09	7,54	11,71
Cluster 3 ** (>)	1,78	1,88	0,06	0,24	0,65	1,18	2,44	3,69	4,67	9,32	14,85
ben_preg											
	Mean	Standard deviation	Min	P05	P25	P50	P75	P90	P95	P99	Max
Global population	1,60	2,14	0,04	0,18	0,48	0,99	1,95	3,46	4,47	9,51	28,14
Cluster 1	1,61	2,13	0,05	0,19	0,50	0,99	1,98	3,54	4,44	9,52	28,14
Cluster 2	1,58	2,36	0,04	0,16	0,44	1,00	1,84	3,10	4,50	8,70	23,78
Cluster 3	1,61	1,82	0,12	0,17	0,47	0,97	2,16	3,81	4,52	9,06	12,58

Figure 25: Tables of the statistics of 6 characteristics of the population for the global population and the 3 clusters

Comparison column: * corresponds to a significant difference between averages according to a t-test: * if p-value<0.05, ** if p-value<0.01, *** if p-value<0.001, (<) if Mean Cluster < Mean Population, (>) if Mean Cluster > Mean Population

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7.4 Differential network analysis

We can also explore the impact of determinants on the network structure detected in a biomarker dataset (see section 6.5). When we look at the differences between two networks, generated in two datasets we call this differential network analysis. In this example we go back to the regularised networks we created earlier, but now stratified in two. The stratification can be based on a binomial determinant, for example female and males. It is also possible to compare two independent datasets with equal variables, for example between two countries; here country A compared to country B. The two networks can be compared for equalities (intersection) and differences. The setup of the graph and the use of the sparsity parameters is equal to what is described in section 4.4. The two networks here are based on 19 variables (`phthalates`) with 600 observations in country A and 600 observations in country B.

```

out.mb.set1 = huge(as.matrix(CountryA))
out.mb.set2 = huge(as.matrix(CountryB))

StARS_analysis1 <- huge.select(out.mb.set1, criterion = "stars", verbose = FALSE)
StARS_analysis2 <- huge.select(out.mb.set2, criterion = "stars", verbose = FALSE)

par(mfrow=c(1,2))

A <- StARS_analysis1$refit
colnames(A) <- rownames(A) <- colnames(CountryA)
DataSet.1 <- graph_from_adjacency_matrix(A, mode = "undirected")
plot(cluster_fast_greedy(DataSet.1), DataSet.1, main="Country A")

B <- StARS_analysis2$refit
colnames(B) <- rownames(B) <- colnames(CountryB)
DataSet.2 <- graph_from_adjacency_matrix(B, mode = "undirected")
plot(cluster_fast_greedy(DataSet.2), DataSet.2, main="Country B")

```

Country A

Country B

These are the undirected networks based on the communities detected in the data for country A and country B. Based on the visualisation of these networks next to each other it might be hard to see what the exact differences and similarities are. For this we can make two additional plots, showing either the similarities and the differences.

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7.4.1 Similarities and differences between networks

The plots of country A and B seemed to have some overlapping communities, as well as differences.

Similarities between two networks are defined as:

- correlations which are present in the two countries and,
- which are in the same direction (positive vs. negative)

Differences between two networks are defined as:

- correlations which only exist in one of the two countries
- correlations between the two countries which are not in the same direction (positive in one country, negative in the other)
- differences in strength of the two correlations

```
par(mfrow=c(1,1))
G_inter <- graph.intersection(DataSet.1, DataSet.2)
plot(cluster_fast_greedy(G_inter), G_inter, main = "similarities")
```

similarities

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```
G_diff <- graph.difference(DataSet.1, DataSet.2)
plot(cluster_fast_greedy(G_diff), G_diff, main = "differences")
```


The plots of country A and B seemed to have mainly similarities in the detected communities. The only difference between the countries is the (positive) partial correlation between the variables MiBP and X7ohMMeOP.

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8 Implications and conclusion

The statistical methods discussed in this deliverable provide various strategies to describe the occurrence of mixture patterns in HBM data and to identify potential determinants of these mixture profiles. As each of the methods discussed have different approaches to infer mixtures patterns, we suggest to apply a combination of the methods (if not all), rather than one or two methods, and base inferences on the combined methods.

In our first implementation of the statistical scripts, any weighing approaches that may have been applied in specific HBM programmes for e.g. design aspect or non-response are ignored. For most methods described in this deliverable, weighting approaches have not yet been developed. However, we argue that the correlation structure between the HBM markers is not expected to be dependent on such weighing.

The scripts provided in this deliverable should be viewed as starting point for the analysis and will require 'tailoring' to each specific HBM dataset. WP15 (task 15.1) will demonstrate the application of the script in a set of real-life HBM datasets that will become available within HBM4EU.

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9 References

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10 Annex

The total list of loadings of the first five principal components:

```
write.table(PCASum, file = "PCASum.csv",
            row.names=FALSE, na="", col.names=TRUE, sep=";")

PCASum <- as.matrix(pcaPrint(summary(princomp(HBM4EUDataImputed2, cor=TRUE), loadings =
            TRUE, cutoff = 0.2), digits = 3, n = 5))

## Importance of components:
##                Comp.1   Comp.2   Comp.3   Comp.4
## Standard deviation   3.2909742 2.9514687 2.88208757 2.42903621
## Proportion of Variance 0.1244886 0.1001284 0.09547619 0.06781859
## Cumulative Proportion 0.1244886 0.2246170 0.32009319 0.38791177
##                Comp.5
## Standard deviation   2.17331679
## Proportion of Variance 0.05429087
## Cumulative Proportion 0.44220264
##
## Loadings:
##          Comp.1 Comp.2 Comp.3 Comp.4 Comp.5
## pcb31
## pcb18
## pcb56
## pcb84
## pcb118
## pcb153
## pcb180
## pcb138
## bde17
## bde28          -0.212
## bde71
## bde47
## bde66
## bde100
## bde99
## bde85
## bde154         -0.217
## bde153
## bde138         -0.211
## bde183
## bde190
## bde209
## THM_0         -0.262
## THM_1         -0.256
## THM_1.1       -0.260
## THM_3         -0.258
## CHCL3_0       -0.214
## CHCL3_1
## CHCL3_2
## CHCL3_3
## BROM_0        -0.251
## BROM_1        -0.246
## BROM_2        -0.246
## BROM_3        -0.251
```

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```

## hg
## pb
## Co_1
## Ni_1
## Cu_1
## Zn_1
## As_1
## Se_1
## Mo_1
## Cd_1
## Sb_1
## Cs_1
## Tl_1
## Pb_1
## Co_3
## Ni_3
## Cu_3
## Zn_3
## As_3
## Se_3          0.213
## Mo_3
## Cd_3
## Sb_3
## Cs_3
## Tl_3
## Pb_3
## PFHxS
## PFOA          -0.206
## PFOS          0.225
## PFNA          -0.223
## mPFHxS        -0.233
## mPFOA         -0.219
## mPFOS
## mPFNA         -0.208
## BPA
## DCP24
## DCP25
## bPB
## ePB          -0.213
## mPB           -0.203
## pPB
## BP
## TCS          -0.220
## MEHP
## MEHHP         -0.287
## X5cxMEPP      -0.261
## X2cxMMHP      -0.270
## MEP
## MiBP
## MnBP
## X7ohMMeOP
## MBzP
## MEOHP        -0.293

```

SNMU method results – Clusters 1 and 3

Cluster 1, 699 individuals

The first cluster is composed of 699 individuals. Mixtures 2 and 1 are the preponderant ones followed by the mixtures 4, 5 and 3. The mixtures 2 and 1 alone explain almost 40 % of the exposure. The main characteristic of this cluster is that, except for two flame retardants, the exposure to a lot of different substances present in mixtures 1, 4 and 5 is significantly lower than the exposure of the global population.

Cluster 1	699 individuals
Mixtures	Exposure (%) :
Mixtures 2	19.1
Mixtures 1	18
Mixtures 4	11.7
Mixtures 5	10.4
Mixtures 3	10.1
Mixtures 9	8
Mixtures 8	6.3
Mixtures 7	6.2
Mixtures 6	5.7
Mixtures 10	4.5

Pie Chart Cluster 1 Exposition

Figure 13: Importance of the 10 mixtures in cluster 1 exposure

		Cluster 1			Global population				
Mixture 2	Substances	Mean	Standard.deviation	P95	Mean	Standard.deviation	P95	Comparison	
flame retardants	bde47 (5.47 %)	1.84	2.09	6.57	1.66	1.81	5.35		
flame retardants	bde99 (5.39 %)	1.87	2.17	6.29	1.67	1.87	5.16	* (>)	
flame retardants	bde28 (5.13 %)	1.87	2.17	6.16	1.66	2.02	5.42	* (>)	
flame retardants	bde71 (4.79 %)	1.67	1.94	5.42	1.59	1.98	4.99		
flame retardants	bde66 (4.7 %)	1.82	2.27	5.59	1.66	2.08	5.49		
flame retardants	bde209 (4.65 %)	1.9	2.61	5.96	1.68	2.25	5.3		
flame retardants	bde17 (4.64 %)	1.72	2.12	5.43	1.63	2.09	5.2		
flame retardants	bde138 (4.54 %)	1.74	2.12	5.44	1.6	1.96	5.08		
flame retardants	bde100 (4.19 %)	1.9	2.87	5.61	1.76	2.5	5.33		
flame retardants	bde154 (4.17 %)	1.87	2.83	5.85	1.76	2.52	5.58		
flame retardants	bde153 (4.02 %)	1.82	2.7	5.42	1.71	2.44	5.14		
phenols	DCP24 (3.3 %)	1.71	2.18	5.43	1.63	2.05	5.31		
flame retardants	bde85 (3.21 %)	1.85	2.32	5.87	1.66	2.06	5.29		
flame retardants	bde183 (2.94 %)	1.52	1.74	4.54	1.53	1.86	4.57		
phenols	DCP25 (2.9 %)	1.7	2.31	5.17	1.66	2.22	5.25		
heavy metal	Se_3 (2.35 %)	1.48	1.71	4.29	1.53	1.78	4.57		
flame retardants	bde190 (2.16 %)	1.61	2.21	4.54	1.59	2.16	4.81		
heavy metal	pb (1.49 %)	1.66	2.07	4.95	1.64	2.23	4.88		
phenols	mPB (1.39 %)	1.41	1.3	4.17	1.63	2.6	4.95	* (<)	
phenols	pPB (1.31 %)	1.46	1.4	4.29	1.62	2.48	5.02		
PFAS	PFHxS (1.18 %)	1.66	2.19	4.95	1.7	2.5	4.95		
heavy metal	hg (1.12 %)	1.68	2.58	5.58	1.7	2.41	5.84		
phthalates	MnBP (1.09 %)	1.76	2.11	5.36	1.71	2.21	5.39		
flame retardants	pcb31 (1.09 %)	1.37	1.89	4.09	1.52	1.96	4.93		
heavy metal	Cu_3 (1.05 %)	1.55	1.73	4.41	1.67	2.27	5.08		
phenols	bPB (1.03 %)	1.39	1.53	4.19	1.43	1.71	4.43		

Figure 14: Cluster 1 exposure to mixture 2 (19.1% of the total cluster exposure) and comparison with the global population

Comparison column: * corresponds to a significant difference between averages according to a t-test : * si p-value<0.05, ** if p-value<0.01, *** if p-value<0.001, (<) if Mean Cluster < Mean Population, (>) if Mean Cluster > Mean Population

		Cluster 1			Global population				
Mixture 1	Substances	Mean	Standard.deviation	P95	Mean	Standard.deviation	P95	Comparison	
flame retardants	THM_3 (5.44 %)	1.02	0.768	2.64	1.59	1.85	5.29	*** (<)	
flame retardants	THM_2 (5.37 %)	1.01	0.742	2.52	1.59	1.91	4.98	*** (<)	
flame retardants	THM_1 (5.35 %)	1.03	0.796	2.59	1.58	1.88	5.28	*** (<)	
flame retardants	BROM_0 (5.32 %)	1.06	0.822	2.73	1.61	1.92	5.18	*** (<)	
flame retardants	BROM_3 (5.24 %)	1.06	0.847	2.85	1.61	1.9	5.16	*** (<)	
flame retardants	BROM_1 (5.18 %)	1.07	0.85	2.73	1.6	1.93	5.15	*** (<)	
flame retardants	BROM_2 (5.14 %)	1.06	0.83	2.67	1.61	1.94	5.21	*** (<)	
flame retardants	CHCL3_0 (3.32 %)	0.992	0.707	2.41	1.51	1.69	4.64	*** (<)	
flame retardants	CHCL3_1 (2.8 %)	1.15	1.09	3.16	1.52	1.72	4.72	*** (<)	
flame retardants	CHCL3_3 (2.79 %)	1.06	0.895	2.91	1.51	1.71	4.42	*** (<)	
flame retardants	CHCL3_2 (2.7 %)	1.06	0.835	2.66	1.55	1.82	5.09	*** (<)	
PFAS	PFOA (1.12 %)	1.81	2.23	5.96	1.74	2.14	5.42		
heavy metal	Tl_3 (1 %)	1.4	1.65	4.2	1.53	1.87	4.5		

Figure 15: Cluster 1 exposure to mixture 1 (18% of the total cluster exposure) and comparison with the global population

Comparison column: * corresponds to a significant difference between averages according to a t-test : * si p-value<0.05, ** if p-value<0.01, *** if p-value<0.001, (<) if Mean Cluster < Mean Population, (>) if Mean Cluster > Mean Population

		Cluster 1			Global population			
Mixture 4	Substances	Mean	Standard.deviation	P95	Mean	Standard.deviation	P95	Comparison
heavy metal	Cu_3 (5.13 %)	1.55	1.73	4.41	1.67	2.27	5.08	
heavy metal	Tl_3 (4.83 %)	1.4	1.65	4.2	1.53	1.87	4.5	
heavy metal	Co_3 (4.59 %)	1.55	2.06	5.12	1.68	2.14	5.27	
heavy metal	Cu_1 (4.56 %)	1.34	1.44	4.03	1.61	2.01	5.08	*** (<)
heavy metal	Cs_3 (4.46 %)	1.4	1.56	4.44	1.58	1.89	5.17	* (<)
heavy metal	Pb_3 (4.02 %)	1.55	1.88	4.53	1.7	2.53	5.32	
heavy metal	Cd_1 (3.97 %)	1.45	2.01	4.63	1.66	2.22	5.67	* (<)
heavy metal	Se_3 (3.96 %)	1.48	1.71	4.29	1.53	1.78	4.57	
heavy metal	Zn_3 (3.88 %)	1.62	1.77	4.93	1.67	1.93	5.47	
heavy metal	Tl_1 (3.67 %)	1.25	1.48	3.7	1.59	2.01	4.9	*** (<)
heavy metal	Sb_3 (3.66 %)	1.76	2.69	5.12	1.75	2.6	5.12	
heavy metal	Ni_3 (3.36 %)	1.65	1.89	5.16	1.7	2.19	5.16	
heavy metal	Sb_1 (3.14 %)	1.41	1.65	4.53	1.64	2.05	5.35	** (<)
heavy metal	Co_1 (3.03 %)	1.37	1.51	4.18	1.67	1.98	5.12	*** (<)
heavy metal	Mo_1 (2.95 %)	1.27	1.47	4	1.66	2.25	5.42	*** (<)
heavy metal	Mo_3 (2.83 %)	1.68	2.17	5.36	1.68	2.2	5.42	
heavy metal	Pb_1 (2.41 %)	1.33	1.38	3.88	1.62	2	5.11	*** (<)
heavy metal	Zn_1 (2.4 %)	1.55	1.8	4.77	1.79	2.83	5.48	* (<)
heavy metal	Ni_1 (2.17 %)	1.44	1.79	4.22	1.8	2.33	6.51	*** (<)
phenols	BP (2.11 %)	1.69	2.02	5.97	1.64	1.94	5.31	
phthalates	7ohMMeOP (2.01 %)	1.55	1.61	5.07	1.71	2.06	5.31	
heavy metal	Se_1 (2.01 %)	1.44	1.6	4.66	1.67	3.35	4.97	* (<)
heavy metal	pb (1.92 %)	1.66	2.07	4.95	1.64	2.23	4.88	
heavy metal	As_3 (1.88 %)	1.71	2.41	5.91	1.72	2.31	6.06	
heavy metal	Cs_1 (1.56 %)	1.18	1.23	3.51	1.62	2.59	5.44	*** (<)
phenols	bPB (1.51 %)	1.39	1.53	4.19	1.43	1.71	4.43	
PCBs	pcb84 (1.22 %)	1.34	1.59	4.3	1.67	2.03	5.87	*** (<)

Figure 16: Cluster 1 exposure to the mixture 4 (11.7% of the total cluster exposure) and comparison with the global population

Comparison column: * corresponds to a significant difference between averages according to a t-test : * si p-value<0.05, ** if p-value<0.01, *** if p-value<0.001, (<) if Mean Cluster < Mean Population, (>) if Mean Cluster > Mean Population

		Cluster 1			Global population			
Mixture 5	Substances	Mean	Standard.deviation	P95	Mean	Standard.deviation	P95	Comparison
phthalates	MEHHP (17.5 %)	1.36	1.25	3.99	1.61	2.58	4.83	** (<)
phthalates	5cxMEPP (16.1 %)	1.4	1.41	4.33	1.58	1.99	5.23	* (<)
phthalates	MEHP (11.6 %)	1.38	1.68	3.82	1.56	2.14	4.71	* (<)
phthalates	2cxMMHP (8.92 %)	1.38	1.52	4.26	1.61	2.43	4.85	* (<)
phthalates	7ohMMeOP (3.73 %)	1.55	1.61	5.07	1.71	2.06	5.31	
heavy metal	Ni_1 (1.63 %)	1.44	1.79	4.22	1.8	2.33	6.51	*** (<)
phthalates	MiBP (1.51 %)	1.59	1.76	4.6	1.7	2.6	5.11	
heavy metal	Sb_1 (1.31 %)	1.41	1.65	4.53	1.64	2.05	5.35	** (<)
phthalates	MBzP (1.26 %)	1.63	1.9	5.35	1.74	2.24	6	
heavy metal	Pb_1 (1.25 %)	1.33	1.38	3.88	1.62	2	5.11	*** (<)
heavy metal	Cs_1 (1.21 %)	1.18	1.23	3.51	1.62	2.59	5.44	*** (<)
phthalates	MnBP (1.17 %)	1.76	2.11	5.36	1.71	2.21	5.39	
heavy metal	Mo_1 (1.17 %)	1.27	1.47	4	1.66	2.25	5.42	*** (<)

Figure 17: Cluster 1 exposure to mixture 5 (10.4% of the total cluster exposure) and comparison with the global population

Comparison column: * corresponds to a significant difference between averages according to a t-test : * si p-value<0.05, ** if p-value<0.01, *** if p-value<0.001, (<) if Mean Cluster < Mean Population, (>) if Mean Cluster > Mean Population

Cluster 3, 204 individuals

The third and last cluster is composed of 204 individuals mainly exposed to mixture 1 and characterised by a higher exposure than the global population to most of the substances of that mixture. The mixture 8 also contributed around 19% to the total cluster exposure.

Mixtures	Exposure (%) :
Mixtures 1	42.9
Mixtures 8	18.8
Mixtures 6	7.3
Mixtures 2	5.8
Mixtures 9	5.6
Mixtures 10	4.8
Mixtures 5	4.1
Mixtures 4	4
Mixtures 3	3.5
Mixtures 7	3.1

Pie Chart Cluster 3 Exposition

Figure 19: Importance of the 10 mixtures in cluster 3 exposure

Mixture 1	Substances	Cluster 3			Global population			Comparison
		Mean	Standard deviation	P95	Mean	Standard deviation	P95	
flame retardants	THM_0 (5.6 %)	4.24	2.9	9.77	1.58	1.86	5.2	*** (>)
flame retardants	THM_3 (5.44 %)	4.21	2.84	10.3	1.59	1.85	5.29	*** (>)
flame retardants	THM_2 (5.37 %)	4.25	3.07	8.96	1.59	1.91	4.98	*** (>)
flame retardants	THM_1 (5.35 %)	4.13	3	8.97	1.58	1.88	5.28	*** (>)
flame retardants	BROM_0 (5.32 %)	4.16	3.1	9.28	1.61	1.92	5.18	*** (>)
flame retardants	BROM_3 (5.24 %)	4.15	3.03	10.5	1.61	1.9	5.16	*** (>)
flame retardants	BROM_1 (5.18 %)	4.09	3.17	8.96	1.6	1.93	5.15	*** (>)
flame retardants	BROM_2 (5.14 %)	4.13	3.16	9.66	1.61	1.94	5.21	*** (>)
flame retardants	CHCL3_0 (3.32 %)	3.94	2.57	8.31	1.51	1.69	4.64	*** (>)
flame retardants	CHCL3_1 (2.8 %)	3.52	2.67	8.97	1.52	1.72	4.72	*** (>)
flame retardants	CHCL3_3 (2.79 %)	3.52	2.71	9.34	1.51	1.71	4.42	*** (>)
flame retardants	CHCL3_2 (2.7 %)	3.94	3	9.54	1.55	1.82	5.09	*** (>)
PFAS	PFOA (1.12 %)	1.64	1.76	4.66	1.74	2.14	5.42	
heavy metal	TI_3 (1 %)	1.68	1.95	4.5	1.53	1.87	4.5	

Figure 23: Cluster 3 exposure to mixture 1 (42.9 % of the total cluster exposure) and comparison with the global population

Comparison column: * corresponds to a significant difference between averages according to a t-test: * si p-value<0.05, ** if p-value<0.01, *** if p-value<0.001, (<) if Mean Cluster < Mean Population, (>) if Mean Cluster > Mean Population

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Mixture 8	Substances	Cluster 3			Global population			Comparison
		Mean	Standard deviation	P95	Mean	Standard deviation	P95	
flame retardants	CHCL3_0 (24.2 %)	3.94	2.57	8.31	1.51	1.69	4.64	*** (>)
flame retardants	CHCL3_3 (17.7 %)	3.52	2.71	9.34	1.51	1.71	4.42	*** (>)
flame retardants	CHCL3_1 (14.1 %)	3.52	2.67	8.97	1.52	1.72	4.72	*** (>)
heavy metal	hg (5.23 %)	1.83	2.42	6.33	1.7	2.41	5.84	
heavy metal	As_3 (3.52 %)	1.88	2.4	6.38	1.72	2.31	6.06	
phthalates	MEP (1.34 %)	1.6	1.68	5.67	1.62	2.06	5.03	
flame retardants	bde47 (1.28 %)	1.43	1.25	4.02	1.66	1.81	5.35	* (<)
phthalates	MiBP (1.12 %)	1.68	2.27	5.49	1.7	2.6	5.11	

Figure 24: Cluster 3 exposure to the mixture 8 (18.8 % of the cluster exposure) and comparison with the global population

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R script for the SNMU algorithm:

```
## data loading

#packages
if(!("varhandle" %in%
installed.packages()[,"Package"])){install.packages("varhandle")}
library(varhandle)
if(!("rstudioapi" %in%
installed.packages()[,"Package"])){install.packages("rstudioapi")}
library(rstudioapi)
if(!("plotly" %in%
installed.packages()[,"Package"])){install.packages("plotly")}
library(plotly)#for the heatmap

setwd(dirname(rstudioapi::getActiveDocumentContext()$path))#set the working
directory to the file location
getwd()
datapath<-"expo_test.csv" #file name, is an example file
#The file must be a .csv file formatted: the individuals are the columns and the
substances the rows

data0<-unfactor(read.csv2(datapath,check.names=F,
fileEncoding="native.enc",na.strings =c("NA",""), header=F, quote =
"",stringsAsFactors = FALSE))

data<-t(apply(data0[-1,-1],1,function(x) as.numeric(gsub(",",".",x))))

#transformation (standardize the substance values)
sdvect<-apply(data,1,sd)
sdvect[sdvect==0]<-1
data<-diag(1/sdvect)%*%data

rownames(data)<-gsub("\",",", data0[-1,1])
noms_compound<-rownames(data)

# SNMU function
norm<-base::norm

SNMU<-function(M, r, lami, delta, Delta, maxiter, init) {
  ### fonction permettant d appliquer la SNMU a une matrice sans donnees
  negatives.

  ### Input and parameters
  ### M : (m x n) matrix to factorize.
  ### r : factorization rank
  ### lami : parameter for sparsity
  ### delta : lower bound for sparsity, in [0,1[
```

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```

### Delta          : upper bound for sparsity, in [delta,1]
### maxiter       : number of iterations,
### init          : =1: svds based initialization (default), otherwise
random
### Output (U,V) : solution,  $UV^T \leq M$ ,  $U \geq 0$  sparse,  $V \geq 0$  ("."-
approximately)     $U = W$  et  $V = t(H)$ 

elem_max = function(x) { return (max(0,x)) }

M2<-M
m = nrow(M); n = ncol(M)
U = matrix(NA,nrow=m,ncol=r)
V = matrix(NA,nrow=n,ncol=r)

mu = sp = vector("list", r)
res = vector("list", r)
St = sum(M^2)
Ve = rep(0,r)
Vjmin = rep(0,r)
RMSE = rep(0,r)
RRMSE = rep(0,r)
RRMSE[[1]]<-1

print_iter=100

### NMU recursion
for(k in 1:r){
  print(k)

  if (length(lami)==r)
    lam0 = lami[k]
  else
    lam0 = lami[1]

  ### definition of vectors
  res1 = spl = mul = rep(0,maxiter)

  ### Initialization of (x,y,sigma)
  x = runif(m); y = crossprod(M,x); y = y / norm(matrix(y), '2')
  x = tcrossprod(M,t(as.matrix(y))); sigma = norm(matrix(x), '2'); x = x /
sigma

  if (init == 1) {
    ### Initialization of (x,y,sigma) with optimal rank-one NMF of M using
power method
    for (i in 1:maxiter) {
      y = crossprod(M,x); y = y / norm(matrix(y), '2')
      x = tcrossprod(M,t(y)); sigma = norm(matrix(x), '2'); x = x / sigma
    }
  }

  U[,k] <- x; V[,k] <- sigma * y

  ##### Initialization of Lagrangian variable Lambda
  ### -Performed by block to decrease memory requirment
  Lambda = matrix(NA, m, n)
  indic = 1:floor(m/2)
  Lambda[indic,] = apply(sigma*tcrossprod(x[indic],y)-M[indic,], c(1,2),
elem_max)
  indic = (floor(m/2)+1):m

```

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```

Lambda[indic,] = apply(sigma*tcrossprod(x[indic],y)-M[indic,], c(1,2),
elem_max)

### Alternating optimization

j=0
while ((j<maxiter) && ((j<=1 || res1[j]>1e-4))) {
  j = j+1

  xp = x; yp = y

  ### ***(x,y) Update***
  if (j==1) {
    yt = t(y)
    x = apply(tcrossprod(M,yt) - tcrossprod(Lambda,yt), c(1,2), elem_max)
    lam = lam0*max(x)
    x = apply(x-lam, c(1,2), elem_max)
    x = x / norm(matrix(x), '2')
  }
  else {
    yt = t(y)
    x = apply(tcrossprod(M,yt) - tcrossprod(Lambda,yt), c(1,2), elem_max)
    max.x = max(x)
    if (max.x<lam) {
      lam = max(0.01,0.99*max.x); print('mu changed bcs x equals zero');
    }
    x = apply(x-lam, c(1,2), elem_max)
    x = x / norm(matrix(x), '2')
  }
  if (sum(x>0) < delta*m){
    lam = lam*0.95; print('mu decreased');
  }
  else if (sum(x>0) > Delta*m) {
    lam = lam*1.05; print('mu increased');
  }
  y = apply(crossprod(M,x)-crossprod(Lambda,x), c(1,2), elem_max)
  y = y / norm(matrix(y), '2')
  sigma = (crossprod(x,M)- crossprod(x,Lambda))%*%y
  mul[j] = lam/sigma#####

  ### Check if the solution is non-trivial
  if (sigma>0) {
    mX = max(x); U[,k] <- x/mX
    V[,k] <- (c(y)*c(mX))*c(sigma)
  }
  else {
    print('Lambda changed');
    Lambda = 0.95*Lambda
    y <- V[,k] ### Take y as the previous value
  }

  spl[j] = sum(x==0)/m ### % Sparsity of x at iteration j#####
  res1[j] = (norm(matrix(xp-x), '2') + norm(matrix(yp-y), '2')) / 2 ### %
Convergence criterion#####

  if (j==1) {
    xs = x; ys = y; sigmas = sigma; jmin = j;
  }
  else if ((res1[j] < res1[jmin]) & !(1.75*spl[j] < spl[jmin])) {
    jmin = j; xs = x; ys = y; sigmas = sigma;
  }
  else if ((j==maxiter-1) & (res1[j] > 10*res1[jmin])) {

```

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```

cat('Algorithm did not converge, best stationary point kept (%dth
iteration) \n', jmin)
x = xs; y = ys; sigmas = sigma;
mX = max(x); U[,k] <- x/mX; V[,k] <- as.numeric(sigmas)*(y*mX); j =
maxiter;
}

### % ***Lambda Update***
indic = 1:floor(m/2)
Lambda[indic,] =
apply(Lambda[indic,]+(as.numeric(sigma)*tcrossprod(x[indic],y)-M[indic,])/(j+1),
c(1,2), elem_max)
indic = (floor(m/2)+1):m
Lambda[indic,] =
apply(Lambda[indic,]+(as.numeric(sigma)*tcrossprod(x[indic],y)-M[indic,])/(j+1),
c(1,2), elem_max)

if (j% print_iter ==0) {
cat("factor = ", k, "\t")
cat("Iter = ", j, "\t")
cat("distance = ", res1[j], "\t")
cat("sp = ", sp1[j], "\n")
}
}

ind_cv<-which(mu1!=0)
mu[[k]] <- mu[ind_cv]
res[[k]] <- res1[ind_cv]
sp[[k]] <- sp1[ind_cv]

Mtild<-tcrossprod(U[,1:k],V[,1:k])
RMSE[[k]] <- signif(sqrt(sum((M2 - Mtild)^2)/(m*n)),5)

if(k>1){
RRMSE[[k]]<-RMSE[[k]]/RMSE[[k-1]]
RRMSE[[1]]<-RRMSE[[2]]
}

M <- apply(M - tcrossprod(U[,k],V[,k]), c(1,2), elem_max)

### variance explained
Sr = sum(M^2)
if (k==1) {
Ve[k] <- (1 - Sr/St) * 100 ## the first factor
}
else
Ve[k] <- (1 - Sr/St) * 100 - sum(Ve[1:k-1]) ## other factors

Vjmin[k]<-jmin
}

result = list(U=U, V=t(V), res=res, sp=sp, mu=mu, Ve=Ve, jmin=Vjmin,
RMSE=RMSE,RRMSE=RRMSE)

return(result)
}

##Choice of number of mixtures and run
numberofmixtures<-4
### Input and parameters
### M : (m x n) matrix to factorize.

```

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```

### r : factorization rank
### lami : parameter for sparsity
### delta : lower bound for sparsity, in [0,1[
### Delta : upper bound for sparsity, in [delta,1]
### maxiter : number of iterations,
### init : =1: svds based initialization (default), otherwise random
### Output (U,V) : solution, UV^T "<=" M, U >= 0 sparse, V >= 0 ("."-
approximately) U = W et V = t(H)
results<-SNMU(data,r=numberofmixtures,lami=0.1,delta = 0.01,Delta = 1,maxiter =
500,init = 1)

## Results description
## Heatmap
palette <-
colorRampPalette(c("darkblue","blue","lightblue1","green","yellow","red","darkre
d"))

U<-results$U
plot_ly(x=paste("Mixtures", 1:ncol(U)),y=rownames(data),z=U,type =
"heatmap",colors = palette(50)) %>%
  layout(title = "Weight of substances in mixtures",

margin=list(l=250,r=30,t=100,b=50),height=length(rownames(data))*25,width=1000,x
axis=list(side="top"))
#Representation of the different mixtures : the color indicates the weight (0 to
1) of each substance in the mixture.

##Mixture description
ind_zero<--which(apply(U,1,sum)==0)
if(length(ind_zero)==0){ind_zero<-(which(apply(U,1,sum)!=0))}
U2<-U[ind_zero,]
M<-round(sweep(U2,2,apply(U2,2,sum),FUN = "/" ),3)
noms<-noms_compound[ind_zero]

#just reading the U matrix
TMixtures<-lapply(1:numberofmixtures, function(i) {
  ind0<--which(M[,i]==0)
  if(length(ind0)==0){ind0<-which(M[,i]!=0)}

  ordre<-order(M[ind0,i],decreasing = T)

  CompNames<-c("Compound name",noms[ind0][ordre],"")

  CompWeight<-c("Weigth",M[ind0,i][ordre],"")

  T1<-data.frame(CompNames,CompWeight)

  colnames(T1)<-c(paste("Mixture",i),paste("Variance",explained
="",round(results$Ve[i],1), "%"))

  return(T1)
})

tableaux_multiple <- function(df_list, file){
  # Properties
  ifelse(is.null(names(df_list)),headings<-1:length(df_list),headings<-
names(df_list))
  seperator <- paste(replicate(50, "_"), collapse = "")

```

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```

# Create sink path
sink(file)

# Loop over each dataframe, and
for(df.i in seq_along(df_list)){
  # Write heading
  if(headings[df.i] != ""){
    cat(headings[df.i])
    cat("\n")
  }
  # Write CSV
  write.csv2(df_list[[df.i]])
  # Write separator
  cat(separator)
  cat("\n\n")
}

# Close sink
sink()
return(file)
}

#The composition of the different mixtures
tableaux_multiple(TMixtures,"Table_of_mixtures.csv")

## clusters
class = hclust(dist(t(results$V), method="minkowski", p=2), method="ward.D")

jump<-rev(class$height)-
rev(class$height)[c(2:length(rev(class$height)),length(rev(class$height)))]
jump[1]<-0
best_jump<-min(max(which(jump==max(jump)),2),length(rev(class$height)))+1

vect_class<-cutree(class,k=best_jump)

#Dendrogram
plot(class,hang=-
1,lab=FALSE,sub="",xlab="Individuals",main="Dendrogram",ylab="Heights")
rect.hclust(class,k=best_jump,border=c(2:(best_jump+1)))
#Representation of the clusters in a dendrogram.

## Clusters and mixtures and statistical tests
V<-results$V
sum_V<-apply(V[1:numberofmixtures,],2,sum)
if(sum(sum_V==0)!=0){sum_V[sum_V==0]<-1}
V2<-sweep(V[1:numberofmixtures,],2,sum_V,FUN = "/")

ordre_expo<-lapply(1:best_jump, function(i) {
  expo_pourcent<-c()
  n_mixtures<-c()

  ind_cluster<-which(vect_class==i)
  expo_cluster<-V2[,ind_cluster]
  if(length(ind_cluster)!=1){expo_mixtures<-
round(apply(expo_cluster,1,mean),3)*100}else{expo_mixtures<-
round(expo_cluster,3)*100}
  return(order(expo_mixtures,decreasing = T))
})

```

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```

clusters<-lapply(1:best_jump, function(i) {
  expo_pourcent<-c()
  n_mixtures<-c()

  ind_cluster<-which(vect_class==i)
  expo_cluster<-V2[,ind_cluster]
  if(length(ind_cluster)!=1){expo_mixtures<-
round(apply(expo_cluster,1,mean),3)*100}else{expo_mixtures<-
round(expo_cluster,3)*100}
  ordre<-order(expo_mixtures,decreasing = T)
  expo_pourcent<-c(expo_pourcent,"Exposure (%)", expo_mixtures[ordre],"")
  n_mixtures<-
c(n_mixtures,"Mixture",paste("Mixture", (1:numberofmixtures)[ordre]),"")

  result_clustering<-data.frame(n_mixtures,expo_pourcent)
  colnames(result_clustering)<-
c(paste("Cluster",i),paste(length(ind_cluster),"Individuals"))

  return(result_clustering)
})

tableaux_multiple(clusters,"Table_of_clusters_exposure.csv")
#Exposure of the clusters to the different mixtures

T_cluster_final<-lapply(1:best_jump, function(i) {
  ind_cluster<-which(vect_class==i)

  nb_tableau<-
min(which(cumsum(as.numeric(as.character(clusters[[i]][2:(numberofmixtures+1),2]
)))>=50))

  T_colnames<-c("Main", "mixtures", "main
substances", "Cluster", "Mean", "Sd", "Min", "P05", "P50", "P90", "P95", "P99", "Max", "Pop
ulation", "Mean", "Sd", "Min", "P05", "P50", "P90", "P95", "P99", "Max", "Comparison")

  T_cluster_tab<-as.data.frame(setNames(replicate(24,numeric(0), simplify = F),
T_colnames))

  for(j in 1:nb_tableau){

    ind_melange<-which(U[,1:numberofmixtures][,ordre_expo[[i]][j]]!=0)
    noms_compound_melange<-noms_compound[ind_melange]

    expo_cluster<-data[ind_melange,ind_cluster]
    percent_subs<-
U[ind_melange,ordre_expo[[i]][j]]/sum(U[,1:numberofmixtures][ind_melange,ordre_e
xpo[[i]][j]])*100

    if(length(ind_melange)!=1){
      mean_pop<-apply(expo[ind_melange,],1,mean)
      med_pop<-apply(expo[ind_melange,],1,median)
      quant_pop<-t(apply(expo[ind_melange,],1,function(x)
quantile(x,prob=c(0,0.05,0.50,0.90,0.95,0.99,1))))
      sd_pop<-apply(expo[ind_melange,],1,sd)

      if(is.null(nrow(expo_cluster))){
        mean_expo<-mean(expo_cluster)
        quant_expo<-
t(quantile(expo_cluster,prob=c(0,0.05,0.50,0.90,0.95,0.99,1)))

```

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```

sd_expo<-sd(expo_cluster)
}
else{
  mean_expo<-apply(expo_cluster,1,mean)
  quant_expo<-t(apply(expo_cluster,1,function(x)
quantile(x,prob=c(0,0.05,0.50,0.90,0.95,0.99,1))))
  sd_expo<-apply(expo_cluster,1,sd)
}
}
else{
  mean_pop<-mean(expo[ind_melange,])
  med_pop<-median(expo[ind_melange,])
  quant_pop<-
t(quantile(expo[ind_melange,],prob=c(0,0.05,0.50,0.90,0.95,0.99,1)))
  sd_pop<-sd(expo[ind_melange,])

  if(is.null(nrow(expo_cluster))){
    mean_expo<-mean(expo_cluster)
    quant_expo<-
t(quantile(expo_cluster,prob=c(0,0.05,0.50,0.90,0.95,0.99,1)))
    sd_expo<-sd(expo_cluster)
  }
  else{
    mean_expo<-apply(expo_cluster,1,mean)
    quant_expo<-t(apply(expo_cluster,1,function(x)
quantile(x,prob=c(0,0.05,0.50,0.90,0.95,0.99,1))))
    sd_expo<-apply(expo_cluster,1,sd)
  }
}

classement_subs<-order(percent_subs,decreasing = T)

MES<-rep("|",length(noms_compound_melange))
MES[1]<-paste("Mixture",ordre_expo[[i]][j],"
(",clusters[[i]][j+1,2],"%)" ,sep="")

Mclust<-MES
Mclust[1]<-paste(length(ind_cluster),"individuals")

Mpopt<-MES
Mpopt[1]<-paste(ncol(expo),"individuals")

sep<-rep("|",length(noms_compound_melange))
pval<-rep("",length(noms_compound_melange))
p<-c()
for(k in ind_melange){
  p.test<-
tryCatch({t.test(expo[k,],expo[k,ind_cluster],alternative="two.sided")$p.value},
error=function(cond) {return("Pas de valeur")})

  p<-c(p,p.test)
}

pval[which(p=="Pas de valeur")]<-"Test impossible"

pval[which(p<0.05)]<-"* (<)"
pval[which(p<0.01)]<- "*** (<)"
pval[which(p<0.001)]<- "**** (<)"

pval[which(p<0.05)][which(mean_expo[which(p<0.05)]>mean_pop[which(p<0.05)])]<-"*
(>)"

```

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```

pval[which(p<0.01)][which(mean_expo[which(p<0.01)]>mean_pop[which(p<0.01)])]<-
"*** (>)"

pval[which(p<0.001)][which(mean_expo[which(p<0.001)]>mean_pop[which(p<0.001)])]<
-"*** (>)"

sign<-3#significant numbers

stat_show<-1:23

T_cluster<-data.frame(paste(noms_compound_melange, "
(", signif(percent_subs, sign), "%)"), sep, as.vector(signif(mean_expo, sign)), as.vect
or(signif(sd_expo, sign)), as.vector(signif(quant_expo[,1], sign)), as.vector(signif
(quant_expo[,2], sign)),
as.vector(signif(quant_expo[,3], sign)), as.vector(signif(quant_expo[,4], sign)), as
.vector(signif(quant_expo[,5], sign)), as.vector(signif(quant_expo[,6], sign)), as.v
ector(signif(quant_expo[,7], sign)), sep, as.vector(signif(mean_pop, sign)), as.vecto
r(signif(sd_pop, sign)), as.vector(signif(quant_pop[,1], sign)), as.vector(signif(qu
ant_pop[,2], sign)), as.vector(signif(quant_pop[,3], sign)), as.vector(signif(quant_
pop[,4], sign)), as.vector(signif(quant_pop[,5], sign)), as.vector(signif(quant_pop[
,6], sign)), as.vector(signif(quant_pop[,7], sign)), pval)
T_cluster<-T_cluster[classement_subs,]

T_cluster<-data.frame(MES, T_cluster)[stat_show]
colnames(T_cluster)=T_colnames[stat_show]

lignevide<-data.frame(t(rep("", length(stat_show))))
colnames(lignevide)<-T_colnames[stat_show]

T_cluster$Cluster<-Mclust
T_cluster$Population<-Mpop

T_cluster<-rbind(T_cluster, lignevide)

T_cluster_tab<-rbind(T_cluster_tab, T_cluster)
}

return(T_cluster_tab)
})

tableaux_multiple(T_cluster_final, "Table_of_clusters_exposure_statistics.csv")
#Statistics of the exposure of the different clusters to the mixtures and
comparison with the exposure of the global population.

```